

NO‘XAT O‘SIMLIGINI DON OG‘IRLIGI KO‘RSATKICHLARIGA SHO‘RLANISHNING TA‘SIRI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada no‘xat navlarining 1000 ta don vazniga sho‘rlanishning ta‘siri natijalari yoritilgan. Sho‘rlanish ta‘sirida no‘xat navlarining 1000 ta don og‘irligi nazorat navlariga nisbatan 19,4 % ga kam bo‘ldi.

Kalit so‘zlar: No‘xat, 1000 ta don vazni, sho‘rlanish, abiotik stress, don soni, oqsil, moy, iqlim o‘zgarishi.

Аннотация. В данной статье приведены результаты влияния засоления на массу 1000 зерен сортов нута. Под влиянием засоления масса 1000 зерен сортов гороха снизилась на 19,4 % по сравнению с контрольными сортами.

Ключевые слова: Горох, масса 1000 зерен, засоление, абиотический стресс, количество зерен, белок, нефть, изменение климата.

Abstract. In this article, the results of the effect of salinity on 1000 grain weight of chickpea varieties are covered. Under the influence of salinity, the weight of 1000 grains of pea varieties decreased by 19,4 % compared to the control varieties.

Key words: Peas, 1000 grain weight, salinity, abiotic stress, grain number, protein, oil, climate change.

Hozirgi kunda dunyo aholisini sifatli o‘simlik oqsili bilan ta‘minlash keskin muammolardan biri bo‘lib kelmoqda. O‘simlik oqsili yetishmovchiligini bartaraf etishning samarali yo‘li dukkakli ekinlarni yetishtirishni kengaytirish va ularning hosildorligini oshirishdir [1]. Dukkakli o‘simliklarni yetishtirish ham tuproq tuzilishini va infiltratsiya darajasini yaxshilaydi, ammo uning ishlab chiqarilishi so‘nggi bir necha o‘n yilliklarda atrof-muhit sharoitlariga qarab o‘zgarib turdi [13]. Ideal atrof-muhit sharoitidagi har qanday o‘zgarishlar, xoh u mo‘l-ko‘llik yoki tanqislik bo‘ladimi, abiotik stress deb hisoblanadi, bu esa o‘sinh va rivojlanishga salbiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi, natijada o‘simliklarning mahsuldorligiga ta‘sir qiladi [14]. Dukkakli ekinlar orasida ekin maydonlari va don yetishtirish bo‘yicha no‘xat dunyoda soya va loviyadan keyin uchinchi o‘rinda turadi. Har yili yer maydonlariga 1,2 mln tonna no‘xat ekiladi va yillik don ishlab chiqarish 9-10 mlntonnaga yetadi [2]. No‘xat doni tarkibida 26-30 % oqsil, 4-7 % moy, 47-60 % azotsiz ekstraktiv moddalar, 2,4-12,8 % kletchatka, 0,2-4 % kul va shuningdek A, B₁, B₂, C vitaminlar va mineral moddalar bor [3].

Tuproq sho‘rlanishining ortishi butun dunyo bo‘ylab qishloq xo‘jaligi ishlab chiqarishiga jiddiy tahdid solmoqda. Global miqyosda 100 dan ortiq mamlakatlarda bir milliard gektardan ortiq er ta‘sir qiladi va bu raqamlar doimiy ravishda o‘sib bormoqda ma‘lumotlariga ko‘ra, hozirgi vaqtda qariyb 1125 million gektar er sho‘rlanishdan aziyat chekmoqda, shundan 76 million gektar odam ta‘siri ostida yuzaga kelgan sho‘rlanishdir [6,7]. Sho‘rlanish o‘simliklarning o‘sishi va hosildorligiga sezilarli ta‘sir ko‘rsatadigan asosiy abiotik stresslardan biridir [4]. Noto‘g‘ri ishlov berish amaliyoti va iqlim o‘zgarishi tufayli ekin maydonlarida sho‘rlanishning doimiy ravishda o‘sishi halokatli global oqibatlariga olib keladi va 21-asrning o‘rtalariga kelib ekin maydonlarining taxminan 50% yo‘qolishi taxmin qilinmoqda [5]. Sho‘rlanish o‘simliklarning hayotiy fiziologik funksiyalarga, ozuqaviy nomutanositliklarga va

gormonal tartibga solishga [9,10], uglerod fiksatsiyasining pasayishiga [8], gullarning tushishiga va gullar va dukkaklar sonining kamayishiga ta’sir qiladi va oxir-oqibatda hosil yetishtirishga to’sqinlik qiladi [11]. Sho‘rlangan sharoitda o‘simliklarning erta reaksiyasi ildiz zonasidan tashqaridagi tuz bilan bog‘liq bo‘lsa, kechki fazadagi tuz stressi ta’siri o‘simlik ichida tuz to‘planishining toksik ta’sirining natijasidir [22]. Dukkakli ekinlarda tuz stressiga nisbatan yuqori sezuvchan bo‘lib, unib chiqish bosqichiga qaraganda ko‘chat va rivojlanish bosqichlarida kuzatiladi [15]. Tuzlilik bir nechta dukkakli ekinlarning o‘shishini cheklaydi, ushbu o‘shish cheklovlari ko‘pincha to‘qimalarning suv potentsialining pasayishi bilan bog‘liq bo‘lib, hujayralar uchun suvning kamroq mavjudligini ko‘rsatadi [16], bu stomatalarning yopilishiga, fotosintezning pasayishiga va o‘shishni inhibe qilishga olib keladi [17]. Mosh o‘simligida sho‘rlanish stressi ostida don sonining kam bo‘lishi va don vaznining kamayganligini o‘rganilgan [12]. Sho‘rlanish soyada ko‘saklar sonini va urug‘ vaznini kamaytiradi [20]. Bundan tashqari tuz stressi ta’sirida dukkakli o‘simliklarning oqsil va yog tarkibining kamayishiga ham sabab bo‘ladi [21]. No‘xat o‘simligida urug‘larning bujmayishi tufayli yakuniy hosilning pasayishiga va don vaznining 20% ga kamayishi kuzatilgan [18,19].

Material va uslublar: No‘xatning mahalliy Guliston, Darmon, Polvon navlaridan Navoiy viloyatining o‘rtacha sho‘rlangan tuproqlarida va Toshkent viloyatining sho‘rlanmagan tuproqlarida ekildi. Bir tup o‘simlikdagi 1000 ta don og‘irligi Vanilla metodi orqali aniqlandi. Olingan ma’lumotlarning statistik tahlili EXCEL 2016 da, ANOVA bo‘yicha Stat View dasturida amalga oshirildi.

Olingan natijalar va ularning tahlili. O‘tkazilgan tajribalarda, Toshkent viloyatida yetishtirilgan no‘xat navlarida 1000 ta don vazni bo‘yicha eng yuqori ko‘rsatkich Darmon navida ($369,73 \pm 0,49$) eng past ko‘rsatkich esa, Polvon navida ($352,48 \pm 4,66$) kuzatildi (1-jadval).

1-jadval

Toshkent viloyatida yetishtirilgan no‘xat navlarining 1000 ta don vazni gr

№	No‘xat navlari nomi	1000 dona don vazni, gr
1	Guliston	$361,09 \pm 11,71$
2	Polvon	$352,48 \pm 4,66$
3	Darmon	$369,73 \pm 0,49$

O‘tkazilgan tajribalarda, Navoiy viloyatining o‘rtacha sho‘rlangan tuproqlarida yetishtirilgan no‘xat navlarida 1000 ta don vazni bo‘yicha eng yuqori ko‘rsatkich Polvon navida ($327,93 \pm 2,4$) eng past ko‘rsatkich esa, Guliston navida ($281,79 \pm 2,56$) qayt etildi (2-jadval).

2-jadval

Navoiy viloyatida yetishtirilgan no‘xat navlarining 1000 ta don vazni gr

№	No‘xat navlari nomi	1000 dona don vazni, gr
1	Guliston	$281,79 \pm 2,56$
2	Polvon	$327,93 \pm 2,4$
3	Darmon	$319,16 \pm 9,08$

Xulosa

Sho‘r lanish ta‘sirida no‘xat o‘simligida ozuqa moddalarining o‘zlashtirilishi va ozuqaviy muvozanatning buzilishi tufayli Navoiy viloyatida yetishtirilgan no‘xat navlarining 1000 ta don vazni Toshkent Viloyatida yetishtirilgan no‘xat navlariga nisbatan 19,4 % kamayganligi aniqlandi.

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